

THE DEVELOPMENT AND EMPLOYMENT STATUS OF SPORTS MANAGEMENT CAREER AND THE CASE OF TURKEY

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Abstract:

Sport management as a young academic discipline experienced remarkable development throughout the world. This improvement has enhanced the need of sport management professionals, and career positions of sport management has received much interest. Therefore, universities have attempted to develop sport management curricula at the undergraduate and graduate levels in order to meet the needs of professionals who are specifically trained in sport management discipline (Tripathi, 2013). In recent years, the number of institutions of higher education in sport management has grown around the world. As a young academic discipline, this remarkable development throughout the world has not been without challenges, problems and controversies (Jones, Brooks, & Mak, 2008). One of the most recently perceived and stated concern is that there are excessive numbers of sport management graduates, which limit employment opportunities. In this regard, aims of this study were to: (1) Provide an overview of the development of sport management programs throughout the world and in Turkey, (2) provide a descriptive critique of sport management graduates' employment status and graduate's employment perceptions in Turkey. For this purpose, a comprehensive literature review was performed with regard to the development and employment status of sports management discipline.

Keywords: sport management, employment, graduate, history, growth

1. Introduction

The sport industry is one of the fastest developing industries in the world (Gillentine, Crow, & Harris, 2009). In line with the sport industry, the sport management academic discipline has improved over the last 50 years since the establishment of the first sport

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management program at Ohio University in 1966 (Laird, 2005; Masteralexis, Barr, & Hums, 1998). This development has increased the need for training of sport professionals throughout the World (Tripathi, 2013), and career positions has received much attention in the sport industry (Gillentine et al., 2009). Universities have attempted to develop sport management curricula at the undergraduate and graduate levels in order to meet the needs of professionals who are specifically trained in sport management discipline (Tripathi, 2013). In recent years, the number of institutions of higher education in sport management has grown around the world. Many students enter academic programs in sport management each year to prepare for a future career in sport (Gillentine et al., 2009). According to Parkhouse and Pitts (2004) sport management discipline has been “*one of the fastest growing areas on college campuses*” (p. 3). The number of sport management programs rose from 20 in 1980 to over 200 by the year 2000 in North America (Mahony, Mondello, Hums, & Judd, 2006). According to the North American Society for Sport Management (NASSM, 2013), there were over 300 degree programs within the United States alone. Number of universities and colleges has increased to 426 in 2013 (Chen, Adams-Blair, & Miller, 2013). Society’s developing involvement in sport has led to advancing interest in sport management as a career. As a consequence, across the United States, approximately 24,000 undergraduate students major in sport management in a given year (Hancock & Greenwell, 2013). There was an almost 82% increase in the foundations providing sport management programs in solely seven years (Mathner & Martin, 2012).

Sport management education is relatively young discipline in Australia, the first degree programme was introduced in 1991 (Smith & Westerbeek, 2004). Smith and Westerbeek identified 37 public and 2 private universities, 10 institutions offer three-year, full-time bachelor degrees in sport management in 2004 in Australia. Smith and Westerbeek reported that approximately 1,500 students were accepted into some form of sport, recreation management bachelor degree or major each year. This exceeds exercise science which is the most intended sport-related topic studied in Australia. The demand and need for sport management major continues to grow persistently while exercise science is decreasing in terms of student interest (Smith & Westerbeek, 2004).

In Turkey, sport management department was established within schools of physical education and sports in 1993. Today, approximately 38 universities have sports management departments. Total number of sport management undergraduate students was 1155 in 2006 (Yıldız, 2008). Number of sport management students who have been accepted to sport management programs including the distance education was increased to approximately 5779 in 2015 in Turkey (www.osym.gov.tr).

Many reasons contributed to the development of sport management as a major. For example, students are attracted to a career in sport by the glamor related to the image of working for a professional team whose games appear on television and sport has increasingly being part of the entertainment industry (Kjeldsen, 1990). For any occupation the image is not always represent the reality, the image of a sport career as well (Kjeldsen, 1990). As a young academic discipline, this remarkable development

throughout the world has not been without challenges, problems and controversies (Jones, Brooks, & Mak, 2008). One of the most recently perceived and stated concern regarding sport management academic discipline is that there are excessive numbers of sport management programs. Hence, there are too many sport management graduates which constrain employment opportunities and salaries for those who wish to work within sport industry (Mathner & Martin, 2012; Minten & Forsyth, 2014). Since growing number of sport management departments are established each year, and the marketplace becomes more competitive, understanding current sport management student populations is vital for the discipline (Hancock & Greenwell, 2013). Investigation of the sport management programs and employment issues is essential for potential students and for the future improvement of sport management discipline as well. Besides, employment of sport management graduates is associated with meeting the physical activity needs of society, providing high quality sport programs, organizations, and sporting events. In Turkey, however, sport management graduates cannot be employed appropriately. There is a huge gap between number of sport management graduates and the ones who can be employed with sport related jobs. A big contradiction in Turkish sport system is that although more than 40.000 physical education and sport department graduates cannot be appointed in Turkey (Ziyagil, 2014). In Turkish sport organizations, 90% of the managers were not graduated from sport related areas since 1989 (Yetim & Şenel, 2001).

A criticism on employment studies is that graduates' expectations and graduates' perspective is scarce in the literature. Studies has focused on the perspective of universities employers, and government; meaning that their views have dominated the debate (McKeown & Lindorff, 2011). There are few research from the perspective of graduates and how graduates make the transition from higher education to careers (Minten & Forsyth, 2014). Several articles were published throughout the 1980s and early 1990s on topics of sport management career preparation (Brassie, 1989), sport management curricular evaluation and needs assessment (DeSensi, Kelley, Blanton, & Beitel, 1990). However, most of these studies were consisted of syllabus and curriculum and these studies lacked the student or alumni attitudes and opinions (Popp, Weight, Dwyer, Morse, & Baker, 2015).

It is very important to support students' career paths so that they can pursue their educational interests as well as deciding realistically about their future career alternatives (Schwab, Dustin, Legg, Timmerman, Wells, & Arthur-Banning, 2013). Since the hope and hopelessness about our future have an important role on our personal productivity (Çiftçi, Gökçel, & Demirkıran, 2015), employment expectations of the university students both affect their school and business success (Çiftçi et al., 2015). Therefore, individuals' perceptions about their employment after graduation have significant importance on their productivity. In order to shed light on sport management students' perceptions with regard to their employment status in Turkey, empirically conducted studies were reviewed. Aims of this study were to: (1) Provide an overview of the development of sport management programs throughout the world

and in Turkey, (2) provide a descriptive critique of sport management graduates' employment status and graduate's employment perceptions in Turkey. In order to reach the intended purpose, related articles were reviewed.

2. Method

In the current study, a comprehensive literature review was performed with regard to the development and employment status of sports management discipline. The information gathered from secondary sources including, library documents, websites, institutional sources and development plans of Turkey were scanned to identify relevant information. The search of the literature was conducted with Ebscohost, SPORTDiscus and Eric library databases for the years up to 2017. The search terms were "sport management employment", "sport administration employment", "sport marketing employment", "sport management history", "sport management career", "sport management development". The search was also conducted in Turkish with the same words. Additional studies were obtained from the reference lists of relevant articles, which were very helpful to reach potentially relevant sources that were not found by the electronic search strategy.

The worldwide development of sport management academic discipline

Globalization of the sport industry is speedily proceeding. This growth necessitates sound administrative practices, as well as individuals who are educated specifically for the unique nature of the sport industry (Gillentine et al., 2009). Thus, the enhanced popularity of sport, and the demand for an efficient management of all resources in that sector, may clarify why sport management, both as an academic discipline and as a professional occupation, has experienced such remarkable growth (Soucie, 1998).

In an attempt to meet this need of a specialized knowledge base and skills in sport management, educational institutions have established sport management degree programs (Kim, 2012). Since the first sport management program initiated in 1966 at Ohio University there have been notable increases in the number of both undergraduate and graduate sport management degree programs (Kim, 2012). Before sport management became an academic discipline, great sports individuals such as Walter O' Malley, president and chief stockholder of the Brooklyn Dodgers Baseball Club, were actively campaigning for an academic program which specified to train professionals to manage sport (Jones et al., 2008). The first sport management master's degree program was established at Ohio University in 1966, by Dr. James G. Mason (Jones et al., 2008). In 1957, Walter O'Malley predicted the future development of sport industry and anticipated the need for professional sport administrators. O'Malley wrote a letter to Dr. James Mason, a faculty member at Ohio University, stating the following: 'I ask the question, where would one go to find a person who by virtue of education had been trained to administer a marina, race track, ski resort, auditorium, stadium, theatre, convention or exhibit hall, a public camp complex, or a person to fill an executive

position at a team or league level in junior athletics such as a Little League baseball, football, scouting, CYO, and youth activities, etc... A course that would enable a graduate to read architectural and engineering plans; or having to do with specifications and contract letting, the functions of a purchasing agent in plant operations. There would be problems of ticket selling and accounting, concessions, sale of advertising in programs, and publications, outdoor and indoor displays and related items.' (Mason, Higgins, & Wilkinson, 198, p. 44). The questions in this letter explicitly describe the human resources needed within the sport industry. As a result of that inquiry, Mason and his colleagues founded a master's-level sport administration program at Ohio University in 1966 (Brassie, 1989). It was the first endeavor to prepare students for jobs in sport-related areas. Afterwards, Saint Thomas University provided the first undergraduate level sport management program and the University of Massachusetts established the second master's degree program in 1971 (Baker & Esherick, 2013). The South Carolina program was also important because it was developed as an independent sport management department, which is not affiliated with a physical education and recreation department (Gillentine et al., 2009).

The idea caught on, since the first master's sport management program initiated at Ohio University, the number of sport management graduate and undergraduate degree programs has increased steadily (Yiamouyiannis, Bower, Williams, Gentile, & Alderman, 2013), and continue to gain growing popularity in the last five decades. By 1978, there were 3 sport management undergraduate programs and 20 graduate programs in the United States (Parkhouse, 1978). In 1992, the total number of degrees offered by universities, including associate, bachelor, masters, and doctorate, totaled 567 in the United States (Lambert, 1999). By 1995, the number more than doubled to 1,173 degrees (Lambert, 1999). Sport management programs' number increased to over 250 programs by 2001 (Kim, 2012). Thoma identified 23 programs in Europe, 8 in Asia, 3 in Africa, and 1 in Oceania in 1993 (Soucie, 1998). North American Society for Sport Management (NASSM), identified 166 universities which offer sport management education in 2003 in United States (Jones et al., 2008). Smith and Westerbeek reported 37 public and 2 private universities, 10 institutions that offer three-year, full-time bachelor degrees in sport management in 2004 in Australia. According to the NASSM website in 2009, there were 382 sport management programs including; 219 Bachelors, 140 Masters and 23 Doctoral programs in the United States (Haan, 2011). Sport Management education is also developing on the global scale. In 2015 international sport management program identified by NASSM has raised to 79, nearly doubling the number of program in 2003 (Zhang, Wang, Min, Chen, & Huang, 2016). Furthermore, some international programs were not included in NASSM's statistics. For instance, more than 20 Chinese educational foundations offer the sport management major degree in 2015, but NASSM included only one university into its list (Zhang et al., 2016). In 2014, there were 429 undergraduate sport management programs, 253 master's programs, and 40 doctoral programs in Africa, Australia, Canada, China, India, New Zealand, Singapore, Taiwan, the United Kingdom (UK), and the United States which

are identified by NASSM (Masteralexis et al., 2011). As the numbers indicate, quantity of sport management programmes has improved to a great extent over the years.

The growth of sport management academic discipline in Turkey

Sports management has emerged as an academic course with the establishment of the first sports academies in Turkey. Sport academies were first established with the goal of raising physical education teachers, coaches and sports managers in 1974-1976 (Mirzeoğlu, 2015). Two departments took place within sport academies. These were; physical education and sport science and sports management departments. In sports management department, management science, sports organizations, Turkish sports organizations, sports facilities management, planning and budget and public relations etc. lessons were taught (Yetim & Şenel, 2001). Considering taught courses, sports management graduate students had a good infrastructure in the field. However, the closure of the youth and sports academies in 1982 has led to a significant reduction in the sources of sports administrators in Turkey (Yetim & Şenel, 2001). Along with the 1982 Council of Higher Education Law, sport academies were closed and existing students were combined to education faculties' physical education teacher departments (Mirzeoğlu, 2015). Therefore, those institutions turned into physical education teacher training institutions, which were a loss for sport management discipline in Turkey (Mirzeoğlu, 2015). In 1984 and afterwards, graduate training started at universities such as Gazi University and Marmara University (Mirzeoğlu, 2015). Although there were no programs directly in the field of sport management, important contributions were made to the field with the conducted thesis studies (Mirzeoğlu, 2015). University departments of physical education and sports has received high school status in 1992 which provided the establishment of several sport related departments within these high schools such as coaching, sport management and recreation (Aktaş & Alpay, 2015). Sport organization and management was appeared as a separate department among the five departments. Thus, sports management has become an independent department for the first time with the establishment of the physical education and sports school. Five departments were established within Hacettepe University including; sport education; training and movement sciences; sports health; psychosocial areas in sport; and sport organization and management (Mirzeoğlu, 2015).

Establishment of the sports sciences association in 1990's and the start of sports sciences congresses, followed by the publication of physical education and sports sciences journals, the researchers had the opportunity to share their studies (Mirzeoğlu, 2015). In sport sciences, 149 Master's, 46 PhD theses and 249 peer reviewed articles a total of 444 studies were completed from the years between 1992 to 1996 in Turkey (Açıkada, 1997). Considering the distribution of these studies; with 153 studies (34.4%) training and movement sciences was the most, with 49 studies (11%) sport organization and management was the least studied areas (Açıkada, 1997). Number of universities, which has sports education, was increased 10 to 39 universities between 1990 to 1998 academic years (Açıkada, 1997). The first sport management master's program was

begun in Abant İzzet Baysal University in 1997. A sport management doctoral program was opened in the same university in 2002 (Mirzeoğlu, 2015). Today, approximately 38 universities have sports management departments. Total number of sport management undergraduate students was 1155 in 2006 (Yıldız, 2008). Number of sport management students who have been accepted to sport management programs including the distance education was increased to approximately 5779 in 2015 in Turkey (www.osym.gov.tr).

Employment in Sport Management Career and Employment Opportunities

In spite of the fact that, there are many job opportunities in sport, the competition for these positions has been and will remain severe and many of them has very low salaries in comparison to the amount of work expected (Tripathi, 2013). Job duties may vary with the area of the sport industry, type of organization, and level of management but all entail business aspects of sport (Tripathi, 2013). There are many benefits associated with working in sport management jobs. Such as, the chance of working with individuals who share a common bond of the love of sport provides a pleasing work setting and health and wellness advantages are usually great in this field (Tripathi, 2013). On the other hand, the rapid growth of the number of sport management departments and excessive number of student intake, has led to a situation where the number of sport management graduates exceeded the number of available career positions, which resulted in unemployment. It is essential to analyze the sport management job climate. Students should be given realistic descriptions of the job climate in order to generate perceptions which assist them to successfully entering the field (Stockdale & Cormier, 2014). Besides, this will allow instructors to tailor the curriculum to enable the students to develop valuable knowledge and skill (Stockdale & Cormier, 2014).

Several articles were published throughout the 1980s and early 1990s on the topics from career preparation (Brassie, 1989), sport management curricular evaluation and needs assessment (DeSensi et al., 1990). However, most of these studies were consisted of syllabus and curriculum and these studies lacked the student or graduate opinions (Popp et al., 2015). Several authors have investigated job opening rates in sport management, sport management programs and the necessary qualification criteria for candidates for these positions, field's professorial position announcements and sport management doctoral programs were investigated (e.g., Jones, Brooks, & Mak, 2008; Mahony, Mondello, Hums, & Judd, 2006; Pedersen, Fielding, & Vincent, 2007; Pedersen & Schneider, 2003; Pedersen, Whisenant, & Schneider, 2005). However, all of these studies were related to academic positions in sport management.

Schwab et al., (2013) addressed the shortage of available careers in sport management. Authors found that most sport management students desire to work in sport as entertainment, however students' specific career goals are ill-defined. On the other hand, Smith and Westerbeek reported that sport management jobs have been rising in Austria over the last decade, jobs reached top in the 2000 Sydney Olympics,

after then the level dropped temporarily and has recovered. Most of the work in the sport management is in the event and facility management sector, which operate with a business orientation rather than performance development (Smith & Westerbeek, 2004). Timmerman, Schwab, Wells, and Dustin (2012), found that approximately two thirds of sport management graduates ended up working in sport, and after a period of time that number was reduced to one-third. Graduates, who remain in the sport industry, reported that their love of sport was a primary motivation for staying in the sport field (Schwab et al., 2013). In a parallel study of Schwab, Legg, Tanner, Timmerman, Dustin and Arthur-Banning (2015) conducted with sport management alumni from five universities that offer undergraduate sport management programs revealed that 63% of the respondents had worked in sport management, at some point since graduation. Nevertheless, of that 63%, 38% reported that they were no longer working in the sport-related field. The primary reasons given for leaving the sport field were limited job opportunities and low salaries. Parks (1991) examined the employment status of alumni of a large sport management program. Author conducted the study to understand demographic information, placement strategies, positions, and salaries, graduate school status. Results revealed that as time progressed from graduation, more alumni were moving out of the field. Respondents also revealed that job placement was dominated by personal contacts, which is especially true for male alumni. Furthermore, respondents' salary related data showed that the sport industry underpays with compared to other industries. These studies reveal that employment rates of the graduates from sport related fields have been decreasing by passing years after graduation. Some of the sport management graduates quit their jobs because of dissatisfaction from the job opportunities. Kjeldsen (1990) examined sport management careers from a descriptive standpoint. The ones who left the field complained about little opportunity for advancement, low pay, unsustainable workloads and poor leadership. On the other hand, Parks and Parra (1994) examined job satisfaction of sport management alumni. They investigated whether there would be a significant difference between job satisfaction scores of graduates who were employed in sport-related positions and the scores of graduates who were employed in positions unrelated to sport. The results revealed that sport management graduates who acquired employment in areas other than sport may have approximately equal prospects of attaining job satisfaction as graduates who were employed in sport-related areas (Popp et al., 2015). In Schwab et al (2013) research, students were asked what areas in sport management appealed to them, students' responses demonstrated various interests. Seventy percent (70%) reported an interest in athletic administration, 62% in personnel management, 57% in marketing, 47% in public relations, 42% in coaching, 32% in recreational sport programming, and 18% in retail. Authors also investigated the reasons to choose sport management as a major and they found that most of the students loved sports and wanted to work in the industry (89%), enjoyed watching sports, (69%) or enjoyed playing sports (67%), (48%) of the students reported that they were interested in issues with regard to sports. Some of the students reported an

interest in sports because of the many perceived job opportunities (39%) or students reported their interest towards community-based programming (16%). Mathner and Martin (2012), examined sport management students' perceptions of career expectations compared with perceptions of sport management practitioners. Students' perceptions were compared to the practitioners' perceptions. Significant differences were found between practitioners and student groups when examining the time, it would take to find an entry-level sport management job. Students perceived a shorter time period as adequate to find an entry-level sport management job with compared to practitioners. Significant results were reported in number of months necessary to reach upper-level management positions, salary perceptions, expected competencies in the field and time to find an entry-level job.

DeSensi et al., (1990) examined university faculty/student evaluation of sport management programs, employer evaluation of educational sport management programs and curricula and employer expectations of sport managers. Employer evaluations revealed that there should be accreditation in order to better prepare students for the job expectations of the sport industry. Because there were differences in the expectations of sport managers in different settings. Sleep and Reed (2006) examined the views of physical education and sport science graduates with regard to the developed work skills at university. The authors find out that according to graduates, university process had helped them to improve interactive and personal skills rather than business specific skills. Cunningham and Sagas (2004) noted that a sport management internship program reduced students' intent to enter a sport occupation. Authors indicated that results were likely due to disconfirmation of expectancies. Students may have an incorrect perception of the sport industry and they were less eager to work in sport after gaining real sport management experiences. The researchers recommend that academicians and advisors should provide students with a realistic preview of the sport industry. Although providing such information, sport management departments run the risk of losing potential students, students will be better equipped to make career choices. Moreover, Cunningham, Sagas, Dixon, Kent, and Turner (2005) examined the effect of internships on students' career-related intentions. Authors found that even though students did not differ at the beginning of the internship, at the end of the internship interns had less positive attitudes toward the sport management occupation than did non-interns. Internship brought a negative perception to previously held positive beliefs about the sport field.

Sport Management Students' Employment Perceptions in Turkey

Jobs in the sport industry involve numerous skills applicable to the sport setting and requires specific skills to the increasingly multifaceted and complex areas (Parkhouse, 1991). Therefore, in order to achieve goals in sport, managers of sport organizations should have adequate background to specific sport setting. A big contradiction in Turkish sport system is that although more than 40.000 physical education and sport department graduates cannot be appointed in Turkey (Ziyagil, 2014). In Turkish sport

organizations, 90% of the managers were not graduated from sport related areas since 1989 (Yetim & Şenel, 2001).

Since the hope and hopelessness about our future have an important role on our personal productivity (Çiftçi et al., 2015). The business expectations of the university students both affect their school and business success (Çiftçi et al., 2015). Therefore, individuals' perceptions about their employment after graduation have significant importance on their productivity. In order to shed light on sport management students' perceptions with regard to their employment status in Turkey, empirically conducted studies were reviewed. The literature suggests that sport management students may choose sport management major because of a love for sport and a desire to do something for their lives, which allowed them to be close to sport (Schwab et al., 2013). Sibson (2010) stated that "*lifestyle, personal interest, and previous sport experience maybe important in student choices of courses*" (p. 384). However, when students asked to specify their career goals, they were less sure about themselves. It can be inferred that students may be driven by a general passion for sport more than a particular career goal (Schwab et al., 2013). For instance, Ardahan, (2010) conducted a study with 156 Turkish graduate students from sport management major and with 130 undergraduate sport management students. In the study, 49% of the graduate students and 35.8% of the undergraduate sports management students reported that when deciding sport management as a major they were unaware about sport managements' employment areas. After graduation 43% of the students were working in different areas than sport management, 57% stated that they were working in a related field to sport management. In a study conducted by Taşmektepligil, Hazar, Ağaoğlu, Öğreten, and Terzioğlu, (2009) with 280 candidate students for physical education and sports high school and 200 undergraduate students of physical education and sports department in Turkey, found that expectations about finding a job related to physical education and sport significantly different according to level of classes. Students' employment prospects were getting worse when students come to upper classes. In a survey given to candidates at the physical education and sport entrance exam, candidates were asked whether they expect to find a job after their graduation. 68.6% of the surveyed candidate men and 73.2% candidate women gave positive responses. However, undergraduate students were not as optimistic as the candidates were. On the other hand, Turgut, Gökyürek, and Yenel (2004) conducted a study with randomly selected 730 sport management and coaching major students from 11 Physical Education and Sports high schools in Turkey. They found that 72.3% of the sport management and coaching students has concerns about their employment after graduation. Besides, "Considering the employment problem when you graduated, are you doing alternative studies?" question was replied 51.6% of "yes" which reveals their concerns about their employment. In a similar vein, Çerez (2004) revealed that 70% of the 4th grade students of physical education and sport were unsure to recommend the school after graduation. Authors conclude that student's reflections were thought to the result of employment limitation and excessive number of graduates in Turkey. In a parallel study of Çiftçi et

al., (2015) with randomly selected 150 sport management students, found that most of the students (40%) think they cannot find a job easily after the graduation, minority of them (21%) think they can find a job which emphasized employment problems and futures of the sport management students as a worrying issue in Turkey. Depending on these results, we can conclude that as sport management students in Turkey approach their graduation degree, their hopelessness level increases. Sport management degree candidates have much more hope related to their employment than sport management major college students. Overall, sport management students in Turkey predominantly have concerns about their employment.

It is important to understand different individuals from different segments. To evaluate any situation from different perspectives we need to understand perceptions of people from varied segments; in a study conducted by Özen, Koçak, Boran, Sunay, and Gedikli (2012), instructors from departments of physical education and sport were surveyed. Selected instructors were on the opinion that sports clubs do not employ enough sport-educated individuals (62.9 %). Most of the instructors (68.6 %) believed that the ministry organization of Turkey does not employ enough physical education and sport graduates. Besides, most of the instructors (70 %) were on the opinion that Turkish Ministry of Youth and Sports staff profile has not adequate educational, socio-economic and cultural background (Özen et al., 2012). In a study with 11 managers, 34 sports federation employees, 55 sports department students and 89 candidate students for the department of physical education and sport concluded that public opinion of sport management profession is not recognized enough in Turkey. Job definition of sport management is not known by public opinion. Sport management education is not recognized enough as well (Uyar & Sunay, 2009). Authors are on the opinion that much more sport managers should be employed in sport clubs in Turkey. In addition, Ardahan (2010) revealed that 60.5% of the sport management students were willing to find jobs in private sector because sport management students' employment chance in public sector is very limited in Turkey. Students try to find ways to get jobs in private sector. After reviewing studies with regard to graduates' employment in Turkey, it was observed that the rapid increase of the sport management departments and parallel increase in student intake, has created a situation where the number graduates surpassed the number of available job positions which caused a high unemployment situation in Turkey.

3. Discussion

Employment and careers of sports graduates influenced by the country's educational and political system, personal characteristics and the industry. The reviewed literature revealed that there is a disproportion between the number of students who are taken to sport management higher education and the employment of these students after graduation. This situation most likely stems from the high number of sports management education programs. Moreover, the investigated studies revealed that

employment rates of the graduates from sport management fields has been decreasing by passing years after graduation. Since, some of the sport management graduates quit their jobs because of dissatisfaction from the job opportunities.

Students do not start higher education with a clear purpose of working in sport industry and most of the students form their career goals as they move through higher education into the post-graduation phase and it is also likely that this career path can change in varied life phases (Minten & Forsyth, 2014). Job definitions in sport management are not well defined in Turkey. Career in the sports sector most often goes from being a star player to being a coach, and from there to being a sporting technical director (Mirzeoğlu, 2015). Thus, acquiring a job depends on how hard applicant makes an effort to connect with other people rather than how knowledgeable s/he is (Mirzeoğlu, 2015).

In the study conducted by Özen et al., (2012) with the sample of academicians, most of the academicians reported that managers of the General Directorate of Youth and Sport in Turkey could not correctly determine the national and international goals of sport between the years of 2004 and 2011. According to the authors, this situation indicates a problem in determining, forming or implementing sports aims of Turkey. In addition, inadequacy of communication and cooperation between sport sciences and sports organizations in Turkey reported by (64.3%) academicians and most of them (74.4%) have the opinion that academic studies were not pursued by the ministry and relevant authorities. Academician's opinions with regard to managers of the General Directorate of Youth and Sport in Turkey represent inability of the managers in keeping up with sport related scientific knowledge. This situation most likely stem from managers who are not graduates of sports management. Indeed, Yetim and Şenel (2001) reported that 90% of the managers in Turkish sport organizations were not graduated from sport related areas since 1989.

Duties related to sport management require proficiency in areas such as coordinating, decision-making, management and marketing, managing conflict, legal and financial affairs, planning and organizing, leadership, and communicating. Individuals should have also enough sporting background to apply these skills appropriately. Therefore, people with the sports background and profession knowledge have higher ability to evaluate and manage sports than the others (Taşmektepligil, et al., 2009). Besides, the duration of adaptation is longer for those who come from different departments and take part in sports business areas (Taşmektepligil, et al., 2009). Based on these reasons, if priority in the employment is given to individuals who get a sport management education, most of the problems associated with the employment of sport management graduates will be reduced to the greatest for Turkey (Taşmektepligil, et al., 2009).

In fact, advocating a view that all those who manage sports should have physical education and sports education background does not keep up with the modern management approach of our time (Uyar & Sunay, 2009). Sports managers who are equipped with sport and management background from different branches can also

provide wider perspectives on sports organizations and management by working together with athletic trainers and sports educators (Uyar & Sunay, 2009). However, it is an identified problem for Turkey that sport management graduates have very low employment in the management levels. For this reason, higher chance should be given to the sports management graduates in the management of sport. Success in sport depends on good management to great extent. In this regard, management profession's importance and necessity should be emphasized and the necessary arrangements should be made so that the sport management graduates can take more roles in sports management (Uyar & Sunay, 2009). According to Koçak, Karakılıç and Alay (1999), inappropriate and inexperienced staff recruiting may be due to the wrong policies of sport organizations and inexperienced or inadequate staff can cause major problems within the organization.

In order to achieve success in any profession, one has to be aware of the field's employment opportunities, recognize the sector and have the skills required by the industry (Ardahan, 2010). In this sense, it is an essential task of higher education to help sport management students in understanding sport industry, sport management career needs and to clarify how sport management students can found career opportunities. In particular, opportunities for work experience were beneficial to make career aims clearer, as well as developing valuable skills with regard to future employability (Minten & Forsyth, 2014). Involvement in the industry during the education process will provide students a better understanding of the employment. In doing so, employment opportunities can also be created while the students are still in school via the agreements with the industry (Ardahan, 2010). Hence, internship opportunities should be provided for students. Cooperation should be arranged between the university and the industry in order to introduce the business world to the students and students can have job experience by this way. In addition, students may be able to realize their strengths and weaknesses before they graduate and they can improve these weaknesses. Field-specific courses should be included in the curriculum of applied courses. Regarding the employment of graduate students, necessary arrangements should be made by the Ministry of Labor and Social Security.

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